

Exploring One Teacher's Attempts to Differentiate Instruction in Remote Learning Environments

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Although prior research, documents, and teachers' experiences have focused on differentiating a single or a sequence of lessons, the study reported here examined teachers' attempts to differentiate every class, every day, over an entire semester. The study focused on the ideas of differentiation presented by Tomlinson to examine how mathematics teachers and math intervention specialists address differentiated instruction in remote learning environments. The study coordinated the documentational approach to didactics and Thompson and Harel's theory of meanings to examine teachers' (schemes of) meanings as they engaged in and discussed their attempts to differentiate instruction in remote learning environments. Analyses involved teachers' Reflective Mappings of Resource System and remote interviews. The findings reported here focus on the case of one mathematics teacher and highlight the importance of teachers' understandings and meanings in their attempts to differentiate instruction and the role digital resources play in supporting or hindering such practices.

Introduction

A number of international treaties and documents have affirmed the right of all children to education (e.g. United Nations General Assembly, 2006). Preparing all students to participate in life within a diverse society is a major educational challenge. According to Suprayogi et al. (2017), "Meeting student differences is challenging since these differences can be related to a large variety of student characteristics such as learner interests . . . cultural background, language level, [and] attitudes" (p. 298). Differentiated instruction aims to deal with the inherent differences between students by providing them with the best possible opportunities to learn and thrive. According to Tomlinson (2017), differentiated instruction "provides avenues to acquiring content, to processing or making sense of ideas, and to developing products so that each student can learn effectively" (p. 1). A long line of research supports the idea that differentiating instruction is a challenging and complex practice (e.g. Moosa & Shareefa, 2019). A variety of reports detail the challenges to teachers' implementation of differentiated instruction, including a lack of teacher preparation time and resources and a disconnect between teachers' understandings and their implementations of differentiated instruction. Furthermore, research has yielded mixed evidence of teachers' actual use of differentiated instruction, from teachers reporting they rarely or occasionally use differentiated instruction practices in their teaching to moderate or high rates of such practices (Roy et al., 2013).

As a consequence of the Covid-19 pandemic, schools have had to adapt to fulfil their many functions, challenging teachers to rethink ways to support their teaching and their students' learning. According to the OECD (2020), an almost universal response to the pandemic has been the use of digital technologies to support teachers, students and their families. Digital technology allows for new solutions to "what people learn, how people learn,

where people learn and when they learn. Unfortunately, not all students have the same access to digital devices and online resources, and access varies greatly across countries (OECD, 2020). In Ireland, students from “socioeconomically disadvantaged backgrounds and students . . . in rural areas were . . . disproportionately affected by the digital divide, particularly in relation to broadband access” (Mohan et al., 2020, p. 67). The pandemic’s restructuring of classrooms to remote or hybrid teaching and learning environments, along with teachers’ motivations to find new and improved ways to support all of their students, makes examination of teachers’ attempts to differentiate instruction in such environments an area prime for research. Therefore, the study presented here focuses on ideas of differentiation presented by Tomlinson (2017) and addresses the following research questions: 1) How do grades 6-12 mathematics teachers understand differentiated instruction? 2) How do grades 6-12 mathematics teachers understand the resources they utilize to support differentiated instruction?

Theoretical Framework

The study “networks” the documentational approach to didactics (Gueudet & Trouche, 2009) and Thompson and Harel’s (Thompson et al., 2014) theory of meanings. The documentational approach to didactics analyses “teachers’ work through the lens of ‘resources’ for and in teaching: what they prepare for supporting their classroom practices, and what is continuously renewed by/in these practices” (Trouche et al., 2018, pp. 1-2). In the documentational approach, resource is grounded in Adler’s (2000) work, which defines a resource as anything likely to ‘re-source’, or “to source again or differently” (p. 207), the teacher’s work. That is, all the “resources that are developed and used by teachers and pupils in their interaction with mathematics in/for teaching and learning, inside and outside the classroom” (Pepin & Gueudet, 2020, pp. 172-173). Such resources include text (e.g. textbooks, worksheets, tests) and other material resources (e.g. calculators); digital-/ICT-based resources (e.g. online textbooks, GeoGebra); discussions between teachers, orally or online; students’ written work; teachers discussions with mathematics teacher educators; and so forth (Pepin & Gueudet, 2020). This conception of resource is particularly germane, since the study’s main focus involved developing models of teachers’ understandings of differentiated instruction as they attempted to differentiate instruction in remote learning environments; that is, as teachers attempted to differentiate instruction using one or more digital resources. The process of documentational genesis results in the development of a document and can be represented by the equation: Document = Resource(s) + Utilization Scheme. According to Gueudet and Pepin (2020), utilization schemes include both procedural schemes (e.g. how to use particular resources) and cognitive schemes (e.g. knowledge about the means that the resource offers).

Thompson and Harel’s (Thompson et al., 2014) theory of meanings is based on Piaget’s notion of assimilation to a scheme and focuses on teachers’ (schemes of) meanings, where a scheme is defined as “an organization of actions, operations, images, or schemes—which can have many entry points that trigger action—and anticipations of outcomes of the organization’s activity” (Thompson et al., 2014, p. 11). Such a focus enables researchers to

identify and examine the assimilation of schemes, and the means for scheme transformation, via accommodation and reflective abstraction. According to Piaget, to understand is to assimilate to a scheme (Thompson et al., 2014). Therefore, attaching meaning (i.e. understanding) is constituted by assimilating to a scheme and the phrase “a person attached a meaning to a word, symbol, expression, statement, or action” means that the person assimilated the word, symbol, expression, statement, or action to a scheme (Thompson et al., 2014). Thompson and Harel’s system address issues of understanding, meaning, and ways of thinking. Such a system allows for discussions of and investigations into in-the-moment and stable understandings (see Table 1). Such a system is productive for the study presented here, which focuses on teachers’ understandings of differentiated instruction and digital resources not only in-the-moment, but also as these understandings potentially become stable; where an understanding becomes stable by repeatedly constructing it anew (Thompson et al., 2014).

Table 1

Definitions of Understanding, Meaning, and Ways of Thinking (Thompson et al., 2014)

Construct	Definition
Understanding (in-the-moment)	Cognitive state resulting from an assimilation.
Meaning (in-the-moment)	The space of implications existing at the moment of understanding.
Understanding (stable)	Cognitive state resulting from an assimilation to a scheme.
Meaning (stable)	The space of implications that results from having assimilated to a scheme. The scheme is the meaning.
Way of Thinking	Habitual anticipation of specific meanings or ways of thinking in reasoning.

As characterized by Thompson and Harel (see Table 1), an understanding is an in-the-moment state of equilibrium. Such a state of equilibrium may occur from assimilation to a scheme (i.e. stable understanding). According to Thompson et al. (2014), “A scheme, being stable, then constitutes the space of implications resulting from the person’s assimilation of anything to it. The scheme is the meaning of the understanding that the person constructs in the moment” (p. 13). Alternatively, an in-the-moment state of equilibrium might be a state the “person has struggled to attain at that moment through functional accommodations to existing schemes . . . and is easily lost once the person’s attention moves on” (Thompson et al., 2014, p. 13). Such understandings are specific to that moment in time and are “typical when a person is making sense of an idea for the first time” (Thompson et al., 2014, p. 446).

Study Participants

In this report, I present the case of one mathematics teacher (Monique), one of 18 teachers to participate in the study. Participating teachers were comprised of 15 teachers and three intervention specialists (i.e. teachers who assist students in inclusive mathematics classrooms with special education and social adjustment needs), were self-selected, and met the following criteria: a) mathematics teacher or math intervention specialist in any of grades 6 to 12 (i.e. teach students of ages 11-18 years); b) teach in a rural school district in the U.S.

state of Ohio; c) have an interest in investigating ways to differentiate instruction; d) have an interest in exploring how grade 6 to 12 mathematics teachers, math intervention specialists, and university mathematics education researchers can work collaboratively online to support mathematics teaching and learning; and e) have the availability and desire to spend approximately 10 hours of online collaboration over the course of 12 weeks. Teachers were asked to choose one element of differentiation to focus on (i.e. content, process, product, environment, affect) and attempt to utilize digital resource (or resources) and implement strategies around this focus for three to five weeks. At the end of three to five weeks, teachers were asked to evaluate the “success” of this implementation (in terms of their students’ learning) and modify their chosen element, introduce a new element altogether, or add a second element to the first for another three to five weeks. By the end of the semester (12 weeks), each teacher completed roughly two to three of these iterations. In addition, teachers were asked to describe their experiences through text (i.e. *Google Docs*), video (e.g. *Flipgrid*), or audio (e.g. *Audacity*) on a weekly basis. Finally, teachers participated in monthly online sessions designed for teachers to share and discuss their experiences with colleagues.

Data Collection

The study employed the reflective investigation methodology (Trouche et al., 2018) for data collection. According to Trouche et al. (2018), the reflective investigative methodology is naturally associated with case studies and grounded by the following five main principles: (1) broad collection of resources; (2) long-term follow up; (3) in- and out-of-class follow-up; (4) reflective follow-up; and (5) confronting a teacher’s views on her documentation work. Although reflective investigation asserts the need for long-term follow-up because “[g]enesis are ongoing processes and schemes develop over long periods of time” (Trouche et al., 2018, p. 6), the study was designed to examine teachers’ initial (or early) engagements with a resource (or sets of resources) or their engagements with a resource (or sets of resources) in novel ways. As such, follow-ups comprised discussions, interviews, and examinations of teachers’ lessons and their descriptions of instruction over the course of 12 weeks. In the end, the study’s data corpus consisted of reflective mappings of each teacher’s resource system, inferred mapping of each teacher’s resource system, video recordings of all online group meetings and individual teacher interviews (online), copies of and internet links to all materials teachers utilized during their lessons, teachers’ weekly descriptions of their experiences, and teachers’ responses to a pre- and post-survey designed to help make their meanings of differentiated instruction and digital resources to support such instruction explicit. The reflective mapping of a teacher’s resource system (RMRS) is a methodological tool created by a teacher where the teacher is asked to draw a map to present their resources in a structured way based on her own reflection (Trouche et al., 2019). Similarly, the inferred mapping of the teacher’s resource system (IMRS), is a methodological tool created by the researcher based on the observations of and interviews with the teachers about their resource work (Trouche et al., 2019).

Data Analysis

To make sense of teachers' attempts to differentiate instruction in remote learning environments required me to develop models of teachers' ways of operating—models that represented my observations of teachers' actions and interactions with their students, colleagues, and other resources (e.g. digital technology). Analyses involved developing models of teachers' understandings in order to explain how these understandings persisted or changed throughout the study. Using data generated from reflective investigation, these models endured or required modifications dependent on the data corpus supporting or contradicting teachers' hypothesized understandings. Such analyses allowed for teachers' understandings to be compared and contrasted and documentation of potential shifts in teachers' ways and means of operating.

Results

Results focus on the case of Monique, a high school mathematics teacher (teaching students of ages 14-16 years). At the start of the study, Monique had taught mathematics for 11-15 years (in the same school), spent between 31-60% of her professional time using the Internet when preparing for instruction, taught in a district where 31-60% of her students come from socio-economically disadvantaged homes, and classified 31-60% of her students as “low achievers in mathematics” and 1-10% of her students as “gifted in mathematics”. Monique was one of eight mathematics teachers (along with two math intervention specialists) who initially operated with a stable understanding of “to demonstrate and allow for a variety of methods and strategies for solving problems.” Teacher responses to a survey provided at the start of the study (pre-survey) illustrating such an understanding included: “Sometimes I present material in different ways with different strategies” and “I show them different ways to solve problems and let them choose what works best for them.” In addition, these ten teachers believed that differentiated instruction was more important, and that their students believed it was more important to student learning than was the case for the remaining eight teachers. Finally, these ten teachers believed providing their students with choices (regarding classroom activities, assignments, and assessment) was important and that “one size” did not fit all students.

During her second individual interview, I confronted Monique—where “confront” is used in the sense of Brousseau to mean a focused comparison; bringing together for careful comparison—with her initial RMRS, resulting in a map illustrating a connected system of resources (i.e. initial Inferred Mapping of Monique's Resource System, IMRS) involving content and practice standards (grade- or course-specific statements of what students should understand and be able to do in their study of mathematics); the course textbook; resources for solving, graphing, and working on problems (e.g. *TI-84 Plus* graphing calculator, paper and pencil); and resources for virtual instruction (i.e. *Zoom*). Monique selected process as her initial focus element. When asked about her use of the *TI-84 Plus* graphing calculator and paper and pencil, Monique indicated that these resources provided her and her students with two different ways “to solve problems graphically and algebraically”—Monique's stable

understandings for these resources. Such understandings fit Monique’s “space of implications,” which were limited to finding ways to provide her students with resources that “allow for a variety of methods or strategies to solve problems.” Although Monique (and her students) utilized variety, when applicable, by solving problems graphically and algebraically, she never varied student working conditions (e.g. individual, pair, group), nor provided students with levels of support, challenge, or complexity. Considering Monique’s experience and confidence with using digital technologies, she was asked to incorporate (over three weeks) Zoom breakout sessions, where students either worked in pairs or groups of three to discuss and solve problems. Monique was asked to move from group to group (i.e. breakout room) to manage discussions and provide support. In addition, Monique was asked to provide pairs or groups with problems of different levels of complexity as needed. The intent of these interventions was to encourage Monique to promote student collaboration and variety in problem complexity and how students demonstrated their understandings. At the end of the three weeks, Monique was interviewed to determine her level of comfort at using and managing the breakout rooms. Monique indicated that she felt students were getting more targeted support and desired to do more.

Next, Monique was asked to implement “tiered” activities and assignments over the next four weeks, where each pair or group of students were given targeted support, challenge, or complexity which Monique designed in advance. At the end of the seventh week, Monique indicated that the time required to design and manage these “tiered” breakout rooms was a bit overwhelming. Online group meetings and individual interviews (with Monique) indicated that she was spending time designing individualized instruction and pairing or grouping students by level of past achievement. As described by Tomlinson (2017), “While it is true that differentiated instruction . . . advocates attending to students as individuals, it does not assume a separate assignment for each learner” (p. 2). Furthermore, the goal of differentiated instruction is to “have students work consistently with a wide variety of peers and with tasks thoughtfully designed not only to draw on the strengths of all members of a group but also to shore up those students’ areas of need” (Tomlinson, 2017, p. 4). These points were addressed with Monique, ideas that she stated “liberated” her from feeling overwhelmed. During the remaining weeks of the semester, Monique rotated pairs and group members and focused on meeting the needs of each group. The last three weeks of the study, Monique introduced and experimented with online collaborative white boards (e.g. *Jamboard*, *AWW* app) for small group collaborative problem solving. The intent of these interventions was to focus Monique’s thinking on providing students with variation in how they learn, collaborate, and demonstrate their understandings.

By the end of the study, Monique’s differentiation of process, as described by Monique during online group meetings and individual interviews, involved allowing students to make sense of the content – by thinking through, grappling with, and using important understandings and skills – at their own pace. Monique’s final RMRS, online group meetings and individual interviews (involving Monique) resulted in a map illustrating a connected system of resources (i.e. final Inferred Mapping of Monique’s Resource System, IMRS)

displayed in Figure 1. Monique determines what to teach based on the (1) state standards and (2) course textbook, in-concert with feedback (i.e. data) she receives from her online interactions with and observations of students (6 and 7). Furthermore, each lesson involves Monique deciding how much she intends her students to use their (3) graphing calculators, (4) laptop (e.g. Jamboard, AWW app), and (5) paper-and-pencil.

Figure 1

Final Mapping of Monique’s Resource System (IMRS)

Finally, due to the data corpus, it is uncertain whether Monique had developed a stable understanding for differentiated instruction as “allowing students to make sense of the content at their own pace” through generalized assimilation, or if such an understanding was only a functional accommodation and will be assimilated to understandings that exhibit a lack of sense making (and focus on “allowing for a variety of methods and strategies for solving problems”) once the study concluded (e.g. long term) or when classes return to face-to-face instruction.

Discussion and Conclusions

As demonstrated here with the case of Monique, coordinating the documentational approach and a theory of meanings not only supported the development of viable models of teachers’ understandings of differentiated instruction, but also the design of interventions with the potential to support transformation to more inclusive understandings. Participating teachers indicated the Covid-19 pandemic forced them “to try new things to provide engaging lessons that incorporate exciting technology and resources for [their] students.” Furthermore, attempts to incorporate new technologies pushed many teachers out of their comfort zones, making them learners alongside their students. Study limitations included the small sample size, the lack of student interviews, and the inability to observe instruction (either in-person or online), observe teachers as they prepare for instruction, interview teachers face-to-face in their own environments, and observe in-person meetings with colleagues. The study’s findings highlight the importance of teachers’ meanings in their attempts to differentiate instruction and the role digital resources play in supporting or hindering such practices. Finally, the study is relevant to the examination of teacher’s work with and on digital resources as a means to support differentiation and builds on and expands existing research on differentiated instruction (e.g. Moosa & Shareefa, 2019) and research employing the

documentational approach (e.g. Trouche et al., 2019), particularly as remote and hybrid teaching and learning continues throughout the U.S. and across the globe.

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